

The relativistic force

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We look at the following figure:

If we view the force $\vec{F}$ in the classical physics, it's clear with the formula $\vec{F} = m \cdot \vec{b}$, at which m the constant mass shall be and $\vec{b}$ the acceleration:

If the mass or the acceleration equal to zero, then the force is equal to zero, too. If $\vec{F} = 0$, with constant mass $m = 0$ or $\vec{b} = 0$ follows. This can be written in short form:

$$\vec{F} = 0 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad m = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \vec{b} = 0$$

Now we view the situation at the relativistic force. To this force see Sandhas [2], chapter 27 p.67 and Greiner [3], chapter 2.7, p.93, formula (70a) at constant mass:

$$\vec{F} = \frac{m}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{\vec{v}^2}{c^2}}} \cdot \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\vec{v}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{\vec{v}^2}{c^2}}} \right) \quad (1)$$

c is the light velocity and $\vec{v}$ the velocity of the body. In the relativistic theory $\vec{b} = \dot{\vec{v}}$ is valid, too. The point over the vector arrow is the differentiation to the time t .

If we assume $\vec{b} = 0$ then $\vec{v}$ is constant. c is constant, too. We obtain:

$$\frac{\vec{v}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{\vec{v}^2}{c^2}}} = \text{const.}$$

with that:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\vec{v}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \right) = 0$$

Thus the force $\vec{F}$ is equal to zero because of equation (1). We have shown the following result:

If the acceleration $\vec{b}$ is zero, the relativistic force $\vec{F}$ is zero, too. This is valid in the case of constant mass. This can be expressed shorter:

$$\vec{b} = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \vec{F} = 0 \quad \text{if} \quad m = \text{const.}$$

Now the question is, if the inversion is valid, too? If the relativistic force $\vec{F}$ is zero, is then - at constant mass - the acceleration $\vec{b}$ equal to zero, too? We assume $\vec{F} = 0$. With the equation (1) we obtain:

$$\frac{m}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad m = 0$$

or:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\vec{v}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \right) = 0$$

with that:

$$\frac{\vec{v}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} = \vec{r} = \text{const.}$$

We introduce the components $\vec{r} = (r_1, r_2, r_3)$ and $\vec{v} = (v_1, v_2, v_3)$. Then we get the system of equations:

$$r_1 = \frac{v_1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_1^2 + v_2^2 + v_3^2}{c^2}}} \quad r_2 = \frac{v_2}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_1^2 + v_2^2 + v_3^2}{c^2}}} \quad (2)$$

$$r_3 = \frac{v_3}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_1^2 + v_2^2 + v_3^2}{c^2}}}$$

Transformed and squared:

$$r_1^2 - \left(\frac{v_1^2 + v_2^2 + v_3^2}{c^2} \right) \cdot r_1^2 = v_1^2$$

$$r_2^2 - \left(\frac{v_1^2 + v_2^2 + v_3^2}{c^2} \right) \cdot r_2^2 = v_2^2$$

$$r_3^2 - \left(\frac{v_1^2 + v_2^2 + v_3^2}{c^2} \right) \cdot r_3^2 = v_3^2$$

We introduce the following abbreviations:

$$r_i^2 =: a_i \quad \text{for } i \in 1, 2, 3 \quad c^2 =: p$$

$$v_1^2 =: x \quad v_2^2 =: y \quad v_3^2 =: z$$

Thus we have the following system of equations:

$$a_1 - \left(\frac{x + y + z}{p} \right) \cdot a_1 = x$$

$$a_2 - \left(\frac{x + y + z}{p} \right) \cdot a_2 = y$$

$$a_3 - \left(\frac{x + y + z}{p} \right) \cdot a_3 = z$$

Transformed:

$$a_1 = \left(1 + \frac{a_1}{p} \right) \cdot x + \frac{a_1}{p} \cdot y + \frac{a_1}{p} \cdot z$$

$$a_2 = \frac{a_2}{p} \cdot x + \left(1 + \frac{a_2}{p} \right) \cdot y + \frac{a_2}{p} \cdot z$$

$$a_3 = \frac{a_3}{p} \cdot x + \frac{a_3}{p} \cdot y + \left(1 + \frac{a_3}{p} \right) \cdot z$$

Written in matrix form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \left(1 + \frac{a_1}{p} \right) & \frac{a_1}{p} & \frac{a_1}{p} \\ \frac{a_2}{p} & \left(1 + \frac{a_2}{p} \right) & \frac{a_2}{p} \\ \frac{a_3}{p} & \frac{a_3}{p} & \left(1 + \frac{a_3}{p} \right) \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix}$$

For this 3×3 -matrix we choose the symbol A . Now we calculate the determinant of the matrix A with the Sarrus rule:

$$\det A = \left(1 + \frac{a_1}{p} \right) \cdot \left(1 + \frac{a_2}{p} \right) \cdot \left(1 + \frac{a_3}{p} \right)$$

$$+ \frac{a_1}{p} \cdot \frac{a_2}{p} \cdot \frac{a_3}{p} + \frac{a_1}{p} \cdot \frac{a_2}{p} \cdot \frac{a_3}{p} - \frac{a_1}{p} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{a_2}{p} \right) \cdot \frac{a_3}{p}$$

$$- \frac{a_1}{p} \cdot \frac{a_2}{p} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{a_3}{p} \right) - \left(1 + \frac{a_1}{p} \right) \cdot \frac{a_2}{p} \cdot \frac{a_3}{p}$$

We can multiply the first horizontal row out:

$$\left(1 + \frac{a_1}{p} + \frac{a_2}{p} + \frac{a_1 a_2}{p^2} \right) \cdot \left(1 + \frac{a_3}{p} \right) = 1 + \frac{a_1}{p} + \frac{a_2}{p} + \frac{a_1 a_2}{p^2}$$

$$+\frac{a_3}{p} + \frac{a_1 a_3}{p^2} + \frac{a_2 a_3}{p^2} + \frac{a_1 a_2 a_3}{p^3}$$

With this insertion we obtain:

$$\det A = 1 + \frac{a_1}{p} + \frac{a_2}{p} + \frac{a_3}{p} > 0$$

The determinant is larger than zero, because of $a_1, a_2, a_3 \geq 0$ and $p > 0$. Because of the determinant being unequal to zero, the matrix A is invertible. With that the matrix has the rank 3. For the dimension of the solution space $\bar{X}$ we get with Fischer [1], chapter 3.3.4, p.123 and 124:

$$\dim \bar{X} = n - \text{rang} A$$

In this case is $n = 3$. With that the solution space $\bar{X}$ has the dimension zero. Thus x, y, z and $\vec{v}$ are not continuous function to the time. At jump discontinuities the acceleration would be infinite. This isn't possible in the macro physics. With that it is valid:

$$\vec{F} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad m > 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \vec{v} = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \vec{b} = 0$$

With that velocity and acceleration must be zero. Thus we have in the relativity theory, too:

$$\vec{F} = 0 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \vec{b} = 0 \quad \text{as far as} \quad m > 0$$

or:

$$\vec{F} = 0 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \vec{b} = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad m = 0$$

References

- [1] Gerd Fischer "Lineare Algebra", Vieweg Verlag Brunswick, 8. edition 1984
- [2] W Sandhas "Theoretische Elektrodynamik - Kurzfassung" university Bonn, Physikalisches Institut, Sommersemester 1982, ISSN-0172-8733
- [3] W.Greiner, J.Rafelski "Theoretische Physik" volume 3A "Spezielle Relativitätstheorie" Verlag Harri Deutsch, Frankfurt on the Main 1984
- [4] Harald Schröer "Particular problems of special relativity theory", Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag, Berlin, 2002